

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART VI. AN ANOMALOUS BEHAVIOUR OF THE PERCHLORATES OF POTASSIUM AND AMMONIUM

BY RAM GOPAL

The spontaneous crystallisation of supersaturated aqueous solutions of barium, sodium and ammonium perchlorates has been studied. It is found that though the solubilities of these perchlorates differ widely, $T_s - T$ does not change very much with prolonged heating and, taken separately, $T_s - T$ is almost a constant for the same solute irrespective of the saturation temperature. The low preheating effect in these electrolytes, as well as in KClO_4 , is probably due to large apparent equivalent volume of these electrolytes; besides, the symmetrical nature of the perchlorate ions and its large apparent ionic volume appear to play an important role.

In an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 284) the anomalous character of the perchlorate of potassium was pointed out to be an exception to the general rule ($c\phi$) suggested to explain the behaviour of supersaturated solutions towards spontaneous crystallisation on prolonged and continuous heating. In spite of the fact that the rule was found to hold good or its failure satisfactorily explained, in about thirty cases (cf. Bose and Chatterji, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 94, where the rule has been extended to non-aqueous solutions), it was not even approximately obeyed by KClO_4 . Apparently no flaw could be detected in the viscosity measurements which were made by the well known method of Scarpa as modified by later workers. The reliability of the apparatus was checked by determining the viscosity of 10% and 20% sugar solutions with its help and comparing the results with the standard values given in the literature which were found to agree within the experimental error. Therefore, η and hence ϕ or $c\phi$ values of KClO_4 solutions must be relied upon. Consequently it was considered desirable to examine the behaviour of other perchlorates in order to ascertain the real factor controlling spontaneous crystallisation in these systems.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The available perchlorates, i.e. NH_4ClO_4 , NaClO_4 and $\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, were recrystallised from conductivity water and dried. The general method used for determining the limits of supersaturation was the same as described in the first paper of this series (*ibid.*, 1943, 20, 183) and the results obtained are recorded in Table I. The data for KClO_4 have also been given for comparison.

TABLE I

Ammonium perchlorate.		Sodium perchlorate.		Barium perchlorate.		Potassium perchlorate.	
T_s .	$T_s - T$.	T_s .	$T_s - T$.	T_s .	$T_s - T$.	T_s .	$T_s - T$.
54°	8.9	92-94°	20	51-53°	9	30°	6.4
60-61	8.9	85-86	19	60-63	9	35	6.6
72-73	11-12	87-88	18	53-55	7	40	6.2
81-82	11-12	79-81	19	66-67	8	45	6.0
57-58	9-10	63-65	19	66-68	7	50	6.4
		75-76	20	71-73	9	55	6.5
				83-85	14(?)	60	6.6

The values of T , the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation, have been omitted for the sake of brevity. It may be mentioned, however, that they do not vary appreciably with heating and therefore they belong to the same class where heating effect is negligible.

DISCUSSION

Table I clearly shows that in all the perchlorates studied here, the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation is, in general, almost a constant or only changes very slightly from the mean value (cf. lines below the table). $KClO_4$ is only slightly soluble, whereas the solubilities of $NaClO_4$ and $Ba(ClO_4)_2$ are very high. The low solubilities of $KClO_4$ and NH_4ClO_4 will give small values of $c\phi$, whereas high solubilities of $NaClO_4$ and $Ba(ClO_4)_2$, will, inspite of high viscosity (hence smaller ϕ values), result in large $c\phi$ values. Hence, although it is possible to explain the low preheating effect in the latter two cases, it is impossible to explain the similar behaviour of the former substances on this ground. We must therefore look for a more widely embracing factor which controls spontaneous crystallisation in these solutions.

Apparent ionic volume, ϕ_r , of ions may be tried as a possible solution, for it will necessarily be involved in the formation of a nucleus of any required size. According to Fajans and Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 674) ϕ_r of ClO_4 ion, at infinite dilution, is by far the largest of almost all the common ions, and may therefore be responsible for the above mentioned peculiar behaviour of perchlorates. As supersaturated solutions are, in general, highly concentrated, the combined effect of both the cation and anion, *i.e.* apparent equivalent volume of the electrolyte concerned, at these concentrations, will not be given by the additivity law which may be expected to hold good at infinite dilutions (cf. Fajans and Johnson, *loc. cit.*). It is therefore necessary to find out apparent equivalent volume ϕ_r of different electrolytes in highly concentrated solutions and then values for perchlorates may be compared with those for other electrolytes possessing either negligible heating effect e.g. KI and KNO_3 , or, marked heating effect, e.g. $BaCl_2$ and $Ba(NO_3)_2$, etc. This might be expected to yield necessary information.

In Table II are given the ϕ_r values of saturated solutions, calculated from density data given in the International Critical Tables (1928, 3, 104). Saturation temperature, wherever possible, has been chosen to be 25° and the exceptions are properly marked out.

TABLE II ,

Temperature = 25° .

	KI*	KNO ₃	Na**	Perchlorates of			BaCl ₂	Ba (NO ₃) ₂
				K.	NH ₄ .	Ba***		
Apparent equiv. volumes	49.62	42.20	49.83	48.17	62.31	60.02	19.6	22.84

* $24.3^\circ C$.; ** $50^\circ C$.; *** $20^\circ C$.

Table II clearly shows that from the point of view of apparent equivalent volume the perchlorates are very like KI and KNO_3 , and widely different from $BaCl_2$ and $Ba(NO_3)_2$, and therefore, if this property at all influences or plays any part in the phenomenon of spontaneous crystallisation, the perchlorates should behave like KI and KNO_3 , and not like $BaCl_2$ and $Ba(NO_3)_2$.

The significance of a large ionic volume may be considered here in some detail. For a particular temperature T , the stable crystal nucleus must be of a definite size in order to avoid its own dissolution and keep intact its activity to start spontaneous crystallisation. The process will entail the coming together of a number of lattice forming units, whether simultaneously or developed catalytically (Harbury, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 382) from single molecules or ions, is immaterial. The particular size is more easily attained, the larger the volume or size of the constituent ions, the smaller the number of ions or molecules will be required to make it up. Hence, although the ϕ values of $KClO_4$ and NH_4ClO_4 are small, they are compensated by a large volume of the lattice forming units resulting in an easy formation of an active crystal nucleus even when heating has deactivated or immobilised many catalytic agents. Thus the number of successful collisions will be sufficient to start spontaneous crystallisation. Furthermore, the symmetrical nature of the perchlorate ion also helps in the formation of the active crystal nucleus. Ephraim ("Inorganic Chemistry", 1939, p. 376) remarks that "the general properties of the perchlorates depend to a large extent on the great atomic volume and the symmetrical nature of the perchlorate ion". That appears to account for the peculiarity of the perchlorates towards prolonged heating as well.

A large ionic volume also promotes, in general, a low hydration. Thus, a large ϕ , also serves to keep the ions free from the water molecular envelope surrounding them and this will naturally help in an easy formation of a germ crystal. Consequently, a large ionic volume of the perchlorate ion helps spontaneous crystallisation in this indirect manner also.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

Received April 20, 1949.

Information for Authors

All papers intended for publication in the Journal should be addressed to the Secretary, Indian Chemical Society, 92, Upper Circular Road, Calcutta. Authors will get 30 copies of reprints free of charge; additional 20 copies may be supplied at Re. 1 per page plus cost of paper and postage on previous intimation. Extra copies of reprints over 50 copies may be charged at the rate of Rs. 4/- per page plus cost of paper and postage.

The requirements of the authors as regard extra reprints are to be intimated to the office as early as possible prior to the final printing.

Authors are requested to enclose line drawings of all the diagrams in their papers drawn in Indian ink on smooth white Bristol board. The drawings should be twice the size they will occupy in the Journal. Authors are particularly requested to reduce the number of diagrams to an absolute minimum.

Communications which have appeared in any other journal shall not be published in this Journal unless this course is specially approved by the Council.

Authors are specially requested to submit clean typescript copies with double lined and marginal spacings. References should be inserted in the body of the subject-matter and not in the form of foot-note. Analytical results should be written as (Found: C,....; H,....; N, etc. C, H, O, N Hl S requires C,....; H,....; O,....; etc....per cent).

Authors are requested to send brief abstracts not exceeding 25 lines along with paper to the Secretary's office.

Papers are published mainly on the authors' responsibility and the Society takes no responsibility for the views expressed therein.

Change of address should be immediately intimated to the office.

No claims will be allowed for copies of Journal lost in the mail or otherwise, unless such claims are received within 90 days of the date of issue.

All communications to be addressed to the Secretary, Indian Chemical Society
92 Upper Circular Road, Calcutta.

Cost of Single Issue	Rs. 2
Annual Subscription	„ 16 (for Fellows)
	„ 20 (for Inland Subscribers)
	„ 24 (for Foreign „)

Completed
16 ✓
24 ✓
30

8/- 24/-
30/- 24/-